
INFLUENCE OF ORGANIC RESIDUES AND SILICON

SOLUBILISING BACTERIA ON *PONGAMIA PINNATA* (KARANJ)

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Abstract:

The present investigation "influence of organic residues and silicon solubilising bacteria on Pongamia pinnata (Karanj)" was carried out at Agro forestry Research Farm, College of Agriculture, Nagpur. There were nine treatments comprising of silicon solubilizing bacteria (SSB) and organic residues and four replications. It was observed that, the application of 5 ml SSB along with 200 g N from VC tree⁻¹ increased availability of N, P and K. Organic carbon content of soil was also improved due to application of 5 ml SSB along with 200 g N from VC tree⁻¹. Thus, 5 ml SSB along with 200 g N from VC tree⁻¹ improved the soil health by improving the soil chemical properties of soil.

Key Words: *Silicon Solubilizing Bacteria, Organic residue, availability of nutrients.*

Introduction:

Karanj (*Pongamia pinnata*) is the fastest growing leguminous tree with the potential for high oil seed production which belongs to family Fabaceae. It's native habitat is in tropical and temperate Asia. The plant is most likely originated in India and where it is one of the most popular oil seed plant. Karanj is also known as Beech, Pongam, Honge, Kanj. 'Pongamia' name is derived from Tamil name of plant viz, 'pongam' or 'pungam'. In latin "pinnata" means 'feathered' and 'glabra' means without hair. It is a nitrogen fixing tree that produces seeds

containing 25-30 per cent oil. It is often planted as an ornamental and shade tree.

The silicon in silicate minerals is surrounded by four oxygen atoms in tetrahedral fashion. The primary and secondary silicate minerals in rocks are mineralized through microbial metabolism and chemical reaction, where the silica is converted and made available to plant. Bacterial metabolic activity in relation to micronutrient fixation in plants is the predominant role in this PGPR organism like iron bacteria, sulphur bacteria, silicon solubilizing bacteria. Bacteria when applied to root, cause alternation in the rhizosphere, where its population persist

and has continuously increases in the ecosystem. Silicon solubilizing bacteria can play efficient role by solubilizing insoluble forms of silicates hence, increasing soil fertility and enhancing plant defence mechanism. Efficient silicate solubilizing bacteria can help release other essential nutrients in soil. Hence, the present study was planned to find out the effect of silicon solubilizing bacteria on availability of nutrients under the different sources of silica.

Material and Methods:

The present investigation entitled “influence of organic residues and silicon solubilising bacteria on *Pongamia pinnata* (Karanj).” was carried at Agroforestry Research Farm, College of Agriculture, Nagpur. The layout of experiment at field was laid out in randomized block design with nine different treatments which were replicated thrice. Different organic residues viz., FYM, VC, bamboo litter, teak litter, CDS and compost were selected as silicon sources. The treatments were T₁- absolute control, T₂- 5 ml lit⁻¹ tree⁻¹ SSB, T₃- 5 ml SSB + 200 g N tree⁻¹, T₄- 5 ml SSB + 200 g N from FYM tree⁻¹, T₅- 5 ml SSB + 200 g N from VC tree⁻¹, T₆- 5 ml SSB + 200 g N from bamboo litter tree⁻¹, T₇- 5 ml SSB + 200 g N from teak litter tree⁻¹, T₈- 5 ml SSB + 200 g N from CDS litter tree⁻¹ and

T₉- 5 ml SSB + 200 g N from compost tree⁻¹. The samples organic sources of were then analyzed for nutrient content. As per treatments the organic residues were applied in the soil.

Results and Discussion:

The initial composite soil sample was collected from the experimental plot and analysed soil properties. The data revealed that the pH of experimental soil was neutral and EC of the soil was found moderately low. The values of available nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium content in initial soil sample were also recorded. It was found that, available N and P of initial soil was 190.89 kg ha⁻¹ and 12.35 kg ha⁻¹ which were found in low level while K of initial soil was 325.19 kg ha⁻¹. The available sulphur and silicon content in initial soil sample observed to 15.25 mg kg⁻¹ and 175.68 mg kg⁻¹.

Nutrient content of different organic sources:

In the present investigation FYM, VC and CDS were procured from AHDS Department whereas compost, bamboo litter and teak leaf litter were taken from Agroforestry Research Farm, Nagpur. Silicon Solubilising Bacteria (SSB) used in this study is a product of VSI, Manjari, Pune and it was collected from there. The samples of organic sources were then

analyzed for nutrient content. It was found that, the highest organic carbon was present in teak leaf litter followed by bamboo litter, whereas highest level of N was observed in VC, the highest C: N ratio was observed in FYM and the lowest one was observed in VC. Anonymus (2011) concluded that, understanding C:N ratios of crop residues and other material applied

to the soil is important to manage soil cover and crop nutrient recycling, providing quality habitat for soil micro-organisms should be the goal in improving soil. Sharma *et al.*, (2009) reported that the highest available NPK content was observed in case of treatments receiving Vermicompost at 10 t ha⁻¹ to and FYM at 25 t ha⁻¹.

Table 1: Nutrient content of different organic sources

Residues	OC %	N%	C:N	P%	K %
Vermicompost	20.05	1.85	10.84	1.91	2.00
Compost	20.89	1.20	17.40	1.00	1.97
Cow dung slurry	47.68	0.50	25.00	0.40	0.50
Farm Yard Manure	20.10	0.50	40.20	0.20	0.50
Bamboo litter	35.50	0.89	36.60	0.072	0.40
Teak litter	35.81	1.00	35.81	0.30	0.40

Effect of silicon solubilizing bacteria and organic N inputs on soil physico-chemical properties and availability of nutrients:

Organic residues have a significant effect on soil properties such as improving soil aggregation and increasing soil water holding capacity and also increasing the exchange and buffering capacity of soils. Along with these residues it has also been suggested that the organosalicic

compounds play a specific role in organic matter formation.

pH and EC (dSm⁻¹):

Soil pH is an important intrinsic property of soil which usually does not change easily. However, long term use of organic materials/inputs has been associated with the decrease in soil pH. Result revealed that soil pH and EC was non significantly influenced by the incorporation of various organic nutrient sources.

Table 2: Effect of silicon solubilizing bacteria and organic N inputs on chemical properties of soil (2017-18)

Treatment	pH	EC (dS m ⁻¹)	O.C (g kg ⁻¹)
T ₁ Absolute control	7.17	0.12	4.87
T ₂ 5 ml lit ⁻¹ tree ⁻¹ SSB	7.15	0.12	5.18
T ₃ 5ml SSB +200 g N tree ⁻¹	7.16	0.13	5.34
T ₄ 5mlSSB +200 g N from FYM tree ⁻¹	7.12	0.12	6.42
T ₅ 5mlSSB+ 200g N from VC tree ⁻¹	7.09	0.12	6.65
T ₆ 5ml SSB +200 g N from Bamboo litter tree ⁻¹	7.13	0.12	6.39
T ₇ 5ml SSB + 200 g N from Teak litter tree ⁻¹	7.10	0.12	5.73
T ₈ 5ml SSB + 200 g N from Cow dung slurry tree ⁻¹	7.09	0.12	5.97
T ₉ 5ml SSB + 200 g N from Compost tree ⁻¹	7.07	0.12	6.24
S. E. ±	0.009	0.001	0.03
C. D. @5 %	-	-	0.07
Initial	7.12	0.12	4.91

After application of treatment the highest soil pH value was (7.17) in treatment T₁- absolute control while, the highest EC of soil was (0.125 dSm⁻¹) was observed in treatment T₇ 5 ml SSB along with 200 g N from teak leaf litter. The lowest values of pH and EC were observed in treatment T₁ absolute control. Mponya *et al.*, (2014) reported that, the application of vermicopmost @ 15 t ha⁻¹ recorded soil pH 7.6 than the control value of pH8.4. Srikant *et al.*, (2000) also reported that, the application of various organic sources FYM, Compost recorded the soil pH between 6.66 to 7.04.

Organic carbon (g kg⁻¹):

The result obtained of soil organic carbon as influenced by various treatments is presented in table 2. Different treatment combinations significantly improved the

OC content of soil. The value of soil OC ranged from 4.87 to 6.65 g kg⁻¹ after application of different organic residue along with SSB to *Pongamia pinnata*. It was found that, there was increase in OC content of soil in different treatments except control where there was depletion in OC. Regarding different treatments, it was observed that, treatment T₅ receiving 5 ml SSB along with 200 g N through VC tree⁻¹ recorded highest OC content i.e (6.65 g kg⁻¹); while, the lowest (4.87 g kg⁻¹) was recorded under treatment T₁ which was absolute control. Treatment T₅ recorded 26.17 per cent increment over initial value and 26.76 per cent over control. Treatment T₅ receiving 5ml SSB along with 200g N through VC tree⁻¹ was found significantly superior over other all treatments for OC content. In all the order of OC content in

different treatments combinations was observed as $T_5 > T_4 > T_6 > T_9 > T_8 > T_7 > T_3 > T > T_1$.

Though organic carbon content in VC was lower as compared CDS and bamboo and teak litter; but after treatment application OC content found more in VC applied plot. The VC which is product of non thermophilic biodegradation of joint action of earthworms and hormones might have resulted in increased OC content of soil (Erashin *et al.*, 2009). Ilkar *et al.*, 2016 also observed increased OC content of soil by application of VC against FYM. Srikant *et al.*, (2000) reported that, incorporation of various compost resulted in increase in organic carbon over control.

Available nitrogen:

Nitrogen is the pre-requisite and most important nutrient for growth of *Pongamia pinnata*. It is needed in adequate amounts especially at initial growth stage.

The results revealed that, available nitrogen ranged from 191.25 kg ha⁻¹ to 299.54 kg ha⁻¹ during course of study. Significantly highest soil available nitrogen was 299.54 kg ha⁻¹

observed in treatment T₅ receiving 5ml SSB along with 200 g N from VC tree⁻¹, followed by treatment T₉ 277.22 kg ha⁻¹ with application of 5 ml SSB along with 200g N from compost tree⁻¹. While, treatment T₇ ranked third by recording 259.68 kg ha⁻¹ available nitrogen which was at par with treatment T₆ and T₄. The lowest available nitrogen 191.25 kg ha⁻¹ was recorded without addition of any inputs in T₁ i.e. absolute control. Treatment T₅ recorded 36.27 per cent and 36.15 per cent increment in available nitrogen over initial and control values respectively.

The organic matter applied to the soil not only increases OC content of soil but also enriches soil with N, P, K, etc. (Zakir *et al.*, 2012). Among various sources used in study VC was the most concentrated source of nitrogen along with P and K. This might be the reason behind highest availability of nitrogen in treatment T₅. Shwetha and Narayana (2014) conducted an experiment on paddy where they found that increased availability of nitrogen with application of VC compare to FYM and inorganic fertilizers.

Table 3: Effect of silicon solubilizing bacteria and organic N inputs on availability of nutrients (kg ha⁻¹) in soil

Treatment	N	P	K
T ₁ Absolute control	191.25	12.37	327.10
T ₂ 5 ml lit ⁻¹ tree ⁻¹ SSB	205.29	13.07	329.67
T ₃ 5 ml SSB +200 g N tree ⁻¹	229.84	13.67	341.83
T ₄ 5 ml SSB +200 g N from FYM tree ⁻¹	254.41	14.13	350.83
T ₅ 5 ml SSB+ 200g N from VC tree ⁻¹	299.54	15.64	356.77
T ₆ 5 ml SSB +200 g N from Bamboo litter tree ⁻¹	259.67	14.88	345.63
T ₇ 5 ml SSB + 200 g N from Teak litter tree ⁻¹	259.68	17.15	348.03
T ₈ 5 ml SSB + 200 g N from Cow dung slurry tree ⁻¹	238.63	15.29	341.43
T ₉ 5 ml SSB + 200 g N from Compost tree ⁻¹	277.22	15.35	346.10
S.E. ±	1.79	0.10	0.28
C.D.@ 5%	5.26	0.29	0.83
Initial	190.89	12.35	325.19

Chitra and Sharavanan (2014), reported that, phosphate solubilizing bacteria (PSB) plays an important role in soil by solubilizing phosphorus and making it available to plants. PSB are potential solubilizers of bound phosphates in soil and vary in their ability to solubilize di and tricalcium phosphate and organic carbon. Further it was correlated with soil nutrients like total nitrogen, organic carbon, and available phosphorous contents.

Available phosphorus:

There was positive impact of SSB and organic residues on availability of phosphorus in soil. The significantly highest soil available phosphorus (17.15 kg ha⁻¹) was observed in treatment T₇ with application of 5 ml SSB and 200g N from

teak litter tree⁻¹ and the second next highest treatment T₅ recorded 15.64 kg ha⁻¹ available phosphorus which received 5 ml SSB and 200 g N from VC tree⁻¹. Treatment T₇ was found significantly superior over other treatments. It recorded 27.98 per cent and 27.87 per cent more available phosphorous than found in initial soil and control plot. The basic mechanisms considered for phosphate solubilization are mediated by production of organic acids (gluconic acid etc) assimilation of ammonium ion or phytase activity. The compost used in the study was made up from forest leaf litter. Though it contains lesser phosphorous than VC its decomposition might have resulted in liberation of different organic acids and thus helped to solubilized more phosphorous from soil. Takeda *et al.*, 2009

observed enhanced soil phosphatase activity was enhanced in compost applied plots which resulted in higher available phosphorous in compost treated plots. They also observed increased fungal population in compost treated plots which might have resulted in solubilization of phosphorous from organic as well as inorganic sources. Sarkar *et al.*, (2010) who reported highest available phosphorous in the soil with Teak leaf litter.

Available potassium:

The availability of potassium among all the treatments ranged from 327.10 kg ha⁻¹ to 356.77 kg ha⁻¹. The observations recorded on soil K content revealed that, during the year of study various treatments of SSB along with different organic residues had significantly influenced the availability of potassium in soil. The significantly superior available potassium (356.77 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded in treatment T₅ which received 5 ml SSB + 200 g N from VC from tree⁻¹ as soil application. While, the lowest available potassium was recorded in treatment T₁ without any external inputs (327.10 kg ha⁻¹). Treatment T₄ with application of 5ml SSB + 200 g N from FYM tree⁻¹ (350.83 kg ha⁻¹) stand second while treatment T₇ with application of 5 ml SSB and 200 g N from teak leaf litter ranked third by recording 348.03 kg ha⁻¹

available potassium treatments T₅ which was significantly superior over other treatments recorded 8.85 per cent available potassium than initial values and 8.31 per cent increased availability of potassium over control. The increasing available K in soil due to addition of organic sources may be described to the reduction of K fixation and release of K due to interaction of organic material with clays besides the direct K addition in the soil. Subehia and Sepehya (2012).

Conclusion:

From the present finding, it was found that, the application SSB along with different organic inputs influence soil chemical and biological properties and growth parameters of *Pongamia pinnata* (Karanj). It can be concluded that, the application of 5ml SSB along with 200gm N from Vermicompost tree⁻¹ improving the soil health by improving the soil physico-chemical properties and plant growth parameters.

In general it can be observed that, the combined use of organic matter like compost, VC with silicon solubilizing bacteria and inorganic fertilizer was helpful for improving soil nutrient status and maintained the fertility of soil which is of utmost significance for sustained productivity. The availability of nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium, sulphur,

silicon increased significantly with the organic matter application over initial status.

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